

INDIA'S INDO-PACIFIC STRATEGIES: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGE MITIGATION

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Abstract

Grounded in the theoretical framework of Neoliberal Institutionalism, this paper examines how India's Indo-Pacific strategy reflects the pursuit of cooperation, interdependence, and institutional engagement in an increasingly complex regional order. The Indo-Pacific, a 21st-century construct linking the Indian and Pacific Oceans, has evolved into a pivotal arena of global trade, maritime governance, and strategic interaction. For India, this vast maritime space presents both opportunities and challenges requiring collaborative responses rather than unilateral action. India's policy emphasises a free, open, inclusive, and rules-based order, built upon partnerships with countries sharing democratic values and common security interests. Through participation in institutional frameworks such as the QUAD, ASEAN-led forums, and the Indian Ocean Rim Association, India advances economic connectivity, maritime security, and disaster management, core elements of neoliberal cooperation. Strengthened ties with the United States, Japan, Australia, France, and ASEAN members further reinforce regional interdependence and collective stability. Confronting issues such as China's assertiveness, technological vulnerabilities, and climate change, India responds through multilateral diplomacy, naval modernisation, and initiatives like SAGAR and the Indo-Pacific Oceans Initiative (IPOI). Viewed through a neoliberal lens,

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India's Indo-Pacific approach prioritises institutional cooperation, shared prosperity, and collective security, aiming to sustain a stable, inclusive, and prosperous regional order.

Keywords: Indo-Pacific strategy, India's foreign policy, QUAD, maritime security, SAGAR, partnership development, challenge mitigation.

I. Introduction

In contemporary global affairs, the Indo-Pacific region has gained prominence as a critical strategic zone. It stretches from the eastern littoral of Africa to the western Pacific Ocean and is home to more than half of the world's population. This area connects some of the busiest sea lanes, major economies, and rising powers. For India, the trajectory is not just a distant physical perception; it is a vital space where its economic growth, security needs, and diplomatic ambitions intersect. India relies on these waters for trade, energy imports, and economic connectivity. At the same time, it faces challenges such as maritime disputes, piracy, terrorism, and the growing influence of other major powers like China. India's approach to the Indo-Pacific has undergone significant changes recently. Earlier, India focused mainly on South Asia and its immediate neighbourhood. Now, it has adopted a broader vision that looks outside the Indian Ocean to the wider Indo-Pacific. This shift is visible in policies like the 'Act East Policy', stronger partnerships with countries including Japan, Australia, and the United States, and initiatives like Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (Quad). India also introduced the idea of Security and Growth for All in the Region (SAGAR), which focuses on inclusive development and collective security for all nations in this region.

It is easier to comprehend the Indo-Pacific strategies of India through the lens of international relations (IR) theory. From a realist view, India is strengthening its naval capabilities, forming strategic alliances, and countering China's assertiveness. This reflects how power politics and national interest drive security decisions. From a liberal perspective, India actively engages in multilateral forums, promotes connectivity, and seeks cooperative solutions to regional challenges, believing that interdependence can lead to stability. From a constructivist perspective, India shapes its policy based on ideas and identity; it wants to be accepted as a responsible, inclusive, and rule-abiding power in the Indo-Pacific, promoting a free, open, and rules-based order.

The Indo-Pacific also offers both opportunities and vulnerabilities. It presents chances for economic growth through trade, blue economy initiatives, and infrastructure development. However, it also faces risks like climate change, illegal fishing, natural disasters, cyber threats, and strategic rivalry among major powers. India must carefully balance these factors while safeguarding its autonomy and sovereignty.

The changing global order reflects another key factor in India's Indo-Pacific engagement. The rise of China, the U.S.-China duopoly, and the enhanced strategic value and growing importance of strategic middle states like Japan and Australia have created new challenges and opportunities for India. By strengthening defence cooperation, improving maritime awareness, and deepening economic ties, India acts as a key actor, aiming to play a proactive role in shaping the future of the Indo-Pacific. This paper argues that India's strategic outreach with the Indo-Pacific goes beyond military security. It also includes diplomacy, trade, connectivity, and cultural exchanges. By looking at India's actions through realism, liberalism, and constructivism, we can better understand how power, cooperation, and shared values will influence its approach. In the coming years, India will continue to evolve as it meets new challenges like technological competition, environmental security, and shifting alliances. This study will explore these aspects in detail, presenting how India balances its strategic, economic, and normative goals to assure peace, prosperity, and stability in the region.

I.I. Why Did India Initially Hesitate to Embrace the Indo-Pacific Concept?

India was initially hesitant to embrace the Indo-Pacific concept in the early 2000s for several reasons. First, India valued its ability to make independent foreign policy decisions, often called 'strategic autonomy,' and did not want to appear aligned with the United States or other Western powers.¹ Second, India was cautious about upsetting China, especially since China was growing closer to Russia, a long-time ally of India.² Third, India is concerned that the Indo-Pacific idea was a U.S.-led plan to contain China, which could harm India's efforts to maintain

¹ Walter C. Ladwig III, "The Indo-Pacific in Indian Foreign Policy," Policy Briefs, April 30, 2024.

² Sarah Tzinieris, Rishika Chauhan & Eirini Athanasiadou, "India's A La Carte Minilateralism: AUKUS and the Quad", *The Washington Quarterly*, Vol. 46, no.4, (2023), p. 21-39, DOI: 10.1080/0163660X.2023.2285540

a balanced relationship with Beijing.³ Finally, India's main focus was securing the Indian Ocean, while early supporters like the United States of America, Japan, and Australia prioritised the Pacific Ocean. A key moment occurred in 2007 when Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe addressed the Parliament of India about the 'Confluence of the Two Seas,' connecting the Indian and Pacific Oceans as a single strategic region. This speech ignited significant discussions about the Indo-Pacific.

India's stance changed due to several factors. First, the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) of China expanded its impact in countries near India, like Sri Lanka, Nepal, Bangladesh, and the Maldives. Namely, Sri Lanka hired out Hambantota port to China for 99 years due to indebtedness, and Bangladesh received Chinese military equipment and port investments.⁴ This made India feel that China was challenging its influence in the Indian Ocean. Second, the 2020 Galwan Valley clash with China, the worst since 1962, worsened relations and showed India it needed stronger military alliances rather than just diplomacy.⁵ Third, India's growing partnership with Japan, which shared concerns about China, was key. In 2015, India and Japan agreed on a vision for a peaceful, open, and rule-based Indo-Pacific. In 2020, they signed the Acquisition and Cross-Servicing Agreement (ACSA), making it easier for their militaries to share supplies like fuel and food. In 2024, the foreign and defence ministers of India and Japan reaffirmed their commitment to international rules, respect for sovereignty, peaceful dispute resolution, and opposition to forceful changes in the region. They also updated their 2008 security agreement to address new threats.

As a result, India overcame its early doubts. While still valuing its independence, India now actively uses the Indo-Pacific framework to

³ Navnit Kumar, "India's Indo-Pacific Strategy: Geopolitical Balance and Economic Integration". *Vedanjali* Vol. 23, no. 1 (January 31, 2025), p. 419–24. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16791990>.

⁴ The Hindu. "Sri Lanka Signs Hambantota Port Deal with China." *The Hindu*, July 29, 2017. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/international/sri-lanka-china-sign-11-bn-hambantota-port-deal/article19385932.ece>.; Indian Defence Research Wing. "Bangladesh's Growing Military Ties with China." *Indian Defence Research Wing*, 2024. <https://idrw.org/bangladesh-handing-over-wwii-airbase-to-china-speculative-says-fr-foreign-minister-of-pakistan/>.

⁵ Center for a New American Security. *The 2020 India-China Border Clash: Implications for the Indo-Pacific*, 2023. <https://www.cnas.org/publications/reports/india-china-border-tensions-and-u-s-strategy-in-the-indo-pacific>.

protect its interests and shape the region with its partnership with Japan playing a central role.

I.II. Why India Embraced the Indo-Pacific: Key Drivers

India initially hesitated to back the idea of Indo-Pacific, but later embraced it due to several key reasons. First, the rising impact of China in South Asia worried India. Through its BRI, China built projects in countries such as Sri Lanka, Nepal, Bangladesh, and the Maldives, which are in proximity to India. For example, Sri Lanka handed over control of the Hambantota Port to China on a 99-year lease after failing to pay back Chinese debt, which gave China a strategic foothold in the Indian Ocean.⁶ Bangladesh also bought Chinese military equipment and received Chinese investments in its ports. This made India feel it was losing influence in its region.⁷

Second, tensions with China, especially the 2020 Galwan Valley clash, the worst since the 1962 war, pushed India to rethink its approach. Ongoing border disputes and Chinese military actions showed India it needed stronger military power and partnerships instead of just trying to get along with China.

Third, India's partnership with Japan grew stronger because both countries were concerned about China's actions. In 2015, they agreed on a vision for a peaceful, open, and rule-based Indo-Pacific.⁸ This allowed India to counter China's influence and shape the region without seeming too aligned with Western countries. In 2020, India and Japan signed the ACSA, which lets their militaries share supplies like fuel and food.⁹ In August 2024, India and Japan's defence and foreign ministers met in New Delhi for their third 2+2 dialogue. They committed to supporting international rules, respecting sovereignty, resolving disputes peacefully, and opposing forceful changes in the region. They

⁷ Center for a New American Security. *The 2020 India-China Border Clash: Implications for the Indo-Pacific*, 2023. <https://www.cnas.org/publications/reports/india-china-border-tensions-and-u-s-strategy-in-the-indo-pacific>

⁸ Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan. *Japan-India Acquisition and Cross-Servicing Agreement (ACSA)*, 2020. https://www.mofa.go.jp/press/release/press4e_002896.html.

⁹ Ibid

also agreed to update their 2008 security cooperation agreement to address new security challenges.¹⁰

II. Review of Literature

The Indo-Pacific region has become a key focus for strategic and security discussions in global politics over the last twenty years. Scholars and policy analysts largely agree that this maritime area, connecting the Indian and Pacific Oceans, is now the hub of global economic and geopolitical activity. Early works by scholars like Rory Medcalf (2014) and David Brewster (2018) show that the Indo-Pacific is not just a geographical concept but also a strategic framework linking major powers, trade routes, and security issues. They argue that factors such as China's rise, the U.S. strategic shift, and the active roles of middle powers like India, Japan, and Australia shape the Indo-Pacific.

In India, several studies have examined New Delhi's evolving foreign policy approach. C. Raja Mohan points out that India's historical focus on South Asia and the Indian Ocean has broadened to encompass a wider maritime vision due to economic globalization and China's assertiveness. Similarly, Harsh V. Pant and Yogesh Joshi assert that India's Indo-Pacific strategy reflects both realist concerns, balancing China's expanding naval strength and liberal values, such as supporting multilateralism and regional cooperation.

The Quad has also drawn notable academic interest. Michael Green describes the Quad as a flexible security arrangement aimed at supporting a free and open Indo-Pacific. Indian scholars like Rajesh Basrur view the Quad as a tool that enhances India's strategic influence while maintaining its strategic independence.

Another important area of study looks at India's maritime security in the Indo-Pacific. David Brewster points out that India has invested in naval modernisation, improved maritime awareness, and formed partnerships with France, Australia, and Southeast Asian countries to protect key sea routes. At the same time, authors like Darshana Baruah emphasize that India's maritime vision also focuses on inclusive growth, blue economy initiatives, and capacity-building for smaller island nations, blending realist and liberal approaches.

¹⁰ Rajagopalan, Rajeswari Pillai. "India-Japan 2+2 Ministerial Dialogue: Strengthening Indo-Pacific Cooperation." *Observer Research Foundation*, (2024). <https://www.orfonline.org/research/india-and-japan-hold-22-ministerial-dialogue>.

From a constructivist perspective, an increasing number of studies explore how ideas, identity, and norms influence India's Indo-Pacific policy. Scholars like Yogesh Joshi argue that India's vision of a "free, open, and rules-based Indo-Pacific" stems from its self-view as a responsible regional power committed to inclusive development. This aligns with the SAGAR policy introduced by Prime Minister Narendra Modi in 2015.

Existing studies also explore non-traditional security issues in the Indo-Pacific, such as climate change, cyber threats, illegal fishing, and disaster response. Authors like Meg Keen and Joanne Wallis argue that India needs to tackle these challenges through collaborative mechanisms, as no single country can manage them alone.

However, gaps remain in the literature. Most studies either concentrate on the India–China rivalry or on India's partnerships with the U.S., Japan, and Australia, while fewer efforts provide an integrated view of India's strategic, security, economic, and normative dimensions in the Indo-Pacific. Many studies address traditional security aspects like naval power and military cooperation, yet there is limited research on how new challenges such as technological competition, environmental security, and digital infrastructure influence India's engagement in the Indo-Pacific.

Additionally, there is an ongoing debate about whether India can preserve its strategic autonomy while strengthening security relationships with like-minded countries. Some scholars claim that India's balancing act between cooperation and competition is delicate, while others regard it as a smart way to maintain flexibility in a multipolar world.

This review indicates that India's involvement in the Indo-Pacific is influenced by several layers, including realist balancing, liberal cooperation, and constructivist identity-building. Still, a comprehensive study that merges these theoretical approaches with an analysis of emerging issues is lacking.

This paper aims to address this gap by examining India's evolving Indo-Pacific strategy through the lenses of realism, liberalism, and constructivism, while also considering new challenges such as climate security, technological rivalry, and changing alliances. By doing this, it contributes to a better understanding of how India is shaping the Indo-Pacific's future.

Understanding India's evolving role in the Indo-Pacific requires a multi-theoretical approach because no single theory fully explains its complex policies. This region involves interactions among security, economics, identity, and power. Therefore, this study utilises three main IR theories, such as realism, liberalism, and constructivism to analyse India's strategic and security aspects.

III. Research Methodology

This study is exploratory in nature, seeking to provide foundational insights into India's evolving Indo-Pacific strategy while encouraging further academic inquiry within this significant theme of international relations. The research adopts an exploratory qualitative research design, which is particularly suited to topics that are still developing or insufficiently defined. As sociologist Robert A. Stebbins explains, exploratory research refers to "a broad-ranging, open-ended investigation designed to gain insights and familiarity for later, more systematic study." Similarly, John W. Creswell notes that exploratory designs allow researchers to identify new themes, generate ideas, and develop understanding where prior theory or data are limited, rather than testing predetermined hypotheses.

The Indo-Pacific, as a geopolitical construct, remains fluid and contested, lacking a universally accepted definition and varying in meaning among regional and extra-regional actors. India's approach to the region is equally dynamic, shaped by a combination of security imperatives and economic ambitions. The growing popularity of the Indo-Pacific concept is closely linked to China's expanding influence and assertive foreign and security policies, both within the region and globally. Countries such as Japan and India stand out for strengthening their security and defense partnerships, largely in response to China's wide-reaching BRI and its strategic ambitions. Thus, an exploratory research design is particularly appropriate, as it permits the researcher to remain open to emerging trends, policy shifts, and interpretive diversity.

While primarily exploratory, this study also incorporates descriptive and analytical dimensions, mapping India's Indo-Pacific vision and major initiatives such as the SAGAR doctrine, the Act East Policy, and its engagements through platforms like the Quad and the Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA). These are then critically examined for their implications on India's long-term strategic objectives.

This study adopts a qualitative research approach as it prioritises an in-depth understanding of ideas, strategies, and policy orientations rather than depending solely on numerical or statistical data. In the discipline

of international relations, where strategic behaviour, power dynamics, and foreign policy discourses are central, qualitative methods provide the analytical depth needed to capture the complexity of state motivations and interactions. Rather than gathering large-scale datasets, this research critically examines policy documents, strategic communications, think tank assessments, and scholarly analyses to interpret how India conceptualises the Indo-Pacific and positions itself within this fluid and evolving regional framework. In methodological terms, the study employs a case study design, focusing on India as the principal case within the Indo-Pacific context. The case study method serves as an analytical lens that enables researchers to explore a specific phenomenon within its real-world policy environment, yielding detailed and context-sensitive insights. As Yin notes, a case study “investigates a contemporary issue within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between the phenomenon and its context are not clearly evident.”³ This design is particularly valuable in international relations research, as it allows for the examination of the strategic behaviour of a single state while facilitating limited comparative analysis with other key actors. Accordingly, while India forms the core of this inquiry, comparisons are drawn with the United States, Japan, and Australia to illustrate points of convergence, divergence, and strategic autonomy in their respective Indo-Pacific engagements.

The research relies on primary and secondary data sources, including official documents and statements like speeches from India's Ministry of External Affairs, summit declarations from the Quad and India-Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN) meetings, and policy papers outlining India's Indo-Pacific Oceans Initiative. Scholarly literature from books, peer-reviewed journals, and think tank reports, such as those published by the Observer Research Foundation (ORF), Brookings Institution, and the Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), provides academic and policy-oriented insights into the region's dynamics. Credible media sources such as *The Hindu*, *Indian Express*, and *The Diplomat* are also consulted to understand contemporary debates and evolving discourses on India's Indo-Pacific policy. Triangulating information from these varied sources helps ensure accuracy and balanced interpretation. To provide structure and a theoretical foundation, the analysis is informed by theories in International Relations (IR). From a Realist or Neorealist perspective, India's Indo-Pacific strategy can be viewed as a response to China's growing maritime and economic influence, emphasizing security-driven motivations. From a Liberal Institutional perspective, India's engagement in multilateral frameworks such as the Quad, IORA, and

ASEAN reflects its preference for cooperative security and a rules-based regional order. Meanwhile, Constructivist theory explains the ideational framing of the Indo-Pacific as a “free, open, and inclusive” space, which reflects India’s attempt to shape the regional narrative beyond mere power politics. By applying a multi-theoretical lens, the study captures both material and ideational dimensions of India’s strategic approach. The data collected is analysed through content and thematic analysis, involving a systematic review of speeches, policy statements, and reports to identify recurring themes, language, and strategic priorities. A SWOT analysis is used to map India’s strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats within the Indo-Pacific region. Additionally, comparative policy analysis examines how India’s approach aligns or diverges from other key Indo-Pacific actors such as the United States and Japan. These analytical tools enable a deeper understanding of opportunities, like increased economic connectivity and maritime partnerships, as well as challenges, including China’s assertiveness and the complexities of balancing relations with multiple stakeholders.

This methodology is suitable because it combines the flexibility of exploratory research with the focus of analytical tools, making it possible to study the complexity of India’s Indo-Pacific strategy effectively. A strict quantitative approach would not capture the indirect and multi-dimensional aspects of India’s foreign policy. In contrast, the qualitative and exploratory framework provides a deeper and more contextual understanding of how India’s role in the Indo-Pacific is evolving, how it addresses various challenges, and how it seeks to take advantage of strategic opportunities. Overall, this approach supports the main goal of the paper to present a comprehensive and balanced analysis of India’s Indo-Pacific strategy within the larger regional and global geopolitical context.

IV. The Indo-Pacific: Global Politics' Hotspot & India's Key Role

The Indo-Pacific region, stretching from the eastern shores of Africa across the Indian and Pacific Oceans, has become the central stage for global politics today. It's where the world's biggest economies trade, powerful militaries operate, and critical issues like climate change and security play out. Within this crucial space, India is increasingly seen as a pivotal player – a nation whose actions significantly shape the region's future. We can understand why this is happening by looking through the lens of IR theories.

IV.I. Why the Indo-Pacific Region Leads Global Discourse?

Imagine the world's busiest shipping lanes, carrying oil, electronics, and food between Asia, Europe, and the Americas. That is the Indo-Pacific. It holds vast resources and is home to over half the world's people. Economically, it is the engine of global growth. Militarily, it's where major powers like the US and China increasingly focus their strength. Conflicts here, disputes over islands or sea lanes, or disruptions to trade, would ripple out to affect everyone globally. It's simply too important to ignore.

IV.II. India's Pivotal Position: Explained by IR Theories

India sits right in the middle of this vital geography. Its importance isn't just location; it's what India does and represents, which IR theories help explain:

(a) Realism: Playing the Power Game (Countering China)

From a Realist perspective, international politics is understood as a continuous struggle for power and survival among sovereign states operating in an anarchic system, one without a central authority to enforce order. In this view, military capability and the ability to ensure one's own security are the key determinants of national power. The rise of China, manifested through its expanding military bases, territorial claims in the South China Sea, and rapid naval modernisation, represents a major shift in the regional balance of power. For India, these developments carry direct strategic implications, both along its contested land borders and within the Indian Ocean, where China's presence has become increasingly assertive.

In International Relations theory, the concept of balancing refers to the strategies states adopt to counter the growing power or threat of another state in order to maintain equilibrium and ensure their survival. Kenneth Waltz describes balancing as a structural imperative—where states build up internal capabilities or form alliances to prevent the dominance of any single power. Stephen Walt further refines this through the Balance of Threat Theory, arguing that states balance not merely against power itself, but against perceived threats, which depend on factors such as geographic proximity, offensive capabilities, and aggressive intentions.

India's response to China reflects both internal and external balancing. Internally, India is strengthening its defence infrastructure, maritime capabilities, and strategic autonomy. Externally, it is forging deeper cooperation with like-minded partners such as the United States, Japan, and Australia through initiatives like the Quad. These efforts

collectively embody India's balancing strategy, aimed at safeguarding its national interests, preserving regional stability, and maintaining a favourable balance of power in the evolving Indo-Pacific landscape.

India's Actions: This explains India's massive naval buildup (new ships, submarines), its crucial role in the Quad (with the US, Japan, and Australia), and its deepening military ties with partners like France and Vietnam. The Quad, especially its military exercises, acts as a powerful counterweight to China. India also builds strategic ports and aids smaller Indian Ocean nations (like Mauritius) to counter Chinese influence. It is a classic realist balancing behaviour.¹¹

(b) Liberalism: Building Rules & Teamwork (Promoting Stability)

Liberals focus on in what manner countries cooperate through shared rules, institutions, and trade to achieve security and prosperity. They believe interdependence reduces conflict. India champions a "free, open, and rules-based Indo-Pacific." This means:

- **Freedom of Navigation:** Ships and trade should move freely without coercion (following the UN Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), 1982).¹²
- **Peaceful Dispute Settlement:** Conflicts should be resolved by agreed rules, not force.
- **Regional Cooperation:** Groups like ASEAN (Southeast Asian nations) should lead the regional structure. India actively participates in forums like the Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA).¹³

(c) Constructivism: Changing Identity & Ideas

Constructivists argue that what matters most is not just power or interests, but how countries see themselves and the world. India's role is

¹¹ Kenneth N. Waltz, *Theory of International Politics* (Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley, 1979), p. 88–97.

¹² Ranjit Seth, "FREEDOM OF NAVIGATION IN THE SOUTH CHINA SEA" *Centre for Joint Warfare Studies*, Vol. 10. No.3, Oct 2016. https://cenjows.in/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Freedom-of-Navigation_03-04-17.doc

¹³ Kim, Misu. "Great Transition in India's Regional Cooperation: Beyond the Neighboring Countries." *The Journal of Indian and Asian Studies* 5, no. 2 (2024): 2440003. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2717541324400035>.

shaped by its evolving identity. It's moving beyond seeing itself *only* as a South Asian power to embracing its destiny as a leading *Indo-Pacific* power. This growing confidence changes its goals and actions.

India's Shift: Its active promotion of the Indo-Pacific concept itself (formally adopted in 2018) reflects this new identity. The idea that India should be a 'net security provider' and take leadership responsibility in the wider region is a powerful new self-perception. How India interprets China's actions (as a threat) and how partners like the US view India (as a crucial democratic counterweight) also actively shape its pivotal role.¹⁴

V. Indo-Pacific and India's Look East Policy to Act East Policy

Over the years, India's foreign policy has evolved significantly, particularly with regard to its neighbours in the east. This shift is mostly due to the expanding significance of the Indo-Pacific region, which encompasses both the Indian and Pacific oceans and is home to numerous significant nations, including the United States, China, Japan, Australia, and ASEAN. India introduced the Look East Policy (LEP) at the beginning of the 1990s. Improving India's political, cultural, and economic ties with Southeast Asian nations was the goal of this policy's introduction. India was opening up its economy and attempting to forge closer ties throughout this period as well.¹⁵ China's increasing influence was one factor contributing to India's interest in the area. In order to counterbalance China's influence without starting a direct conflict, India sought to forge close ties with ASEAN.¹⁶

The relationship between India and Southeast Asia is not new. India and this area had extensive economic and cultural exchanges from the first to the twelfth centuries. Many Southeast Asian nations were influenced by Buddhism, Hinduism, Sanskrit, and Pali.¹⁷ The introduction of Islam and subsequent colonial control, however, caused these ties to

¹⁴ D. Brewster, "*India as an Asia Pacific Power*", (1st ed.). (Routledge, 2012). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203637685>; Alexander Wendt, "*Social Theory of International Politics*", (Cambridge University Press, 1999).

¹⁵ Shantanu Roy-Chaudhury, "From 'Look East' to 'Act East': Mapping India's Southeast Asian Engagement." *ORF Issue Brief* No. 800. Observer Research Foundation, May 2025.

¹⁶ Deepa Ollapally, "China and India: Economic Ties and Strategic Rivalry." *Orbis* 58, no. 3 (2014), p.342–357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orbis.2014.05.003>.

¹⁷ Satish Chandra, "*History of Medieval India*", New ed., (Orient Blackswan, 2020).

deteriorate after the 12th century. Although its strategic significance grew throughout colonial times and World War II, India had little autonomous interaction with the area. Following its independence, India once more prioritised Asian unification. According to their shared history and geography, leaders such as Jawaharlal Nehru aimed to establish solid ties with East Asian nations.¹⁸ However, these attempts were hampered by Cold War tensions and China. India did, however, advocate for peace and participated in the 1953 Korean peace accord.¹⁹ For geopolitical and economic reasons, Prime Minister Narasimha Rao formally introduced the LEP in the 1990s to link India with East and Southeast Asia.²⁰ This was LEP's third phase. During this period, India's ties with ASEAN rapidly expanded. Prior to joining ASEAN-led forums such as the East Asia Summit and ASEAN Regional Forum, India was a Sectoral Dialogue Partner in 1992 and a Full Dialogue Partner in 1995.²¹

This policy was upgraded and called the Act East Policy (AEP) by India in 2014. With this shift, India was actively attempting to strengthen its ties with the East rather than only looking at it. Enhancing connectivity, trade, interpersonal relationships, defence cooperation, and maritime security were the main objectives of the AEP.²² The concept of an inclusive Indo-Pacific (IP), where all nations can develop peacefully without being dominated by one state, was also supported by India.²³

¹⁸ J. Nehru, *The Discovery of India*, (Penguin, 1949.); Panikkar, K. M. *India and the Indian Ocean: An Essay on the Influence of Sea Power on Indian History*. London: Allen & Unwin, 1945

¹⁹ Gonsalves, Eric, and Indian Foreign Affairs Journal. "Resolving the Korean Crisis." *Indian Foreign Affairs Journal* 2, no. 2 (2007): 116–28. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/45340683>.

²⁰ Sudhir Devare, *India and Southeast Asia: Towards Security Convergence*. Singapore: Institute of Southeast Asian Studies, 2005. <https://doi.org/10.1355/9789812305572>.

²¹ S. D. Muni, "Nehru's Successors: Realism Takes Command." Chapter. In *India's Foreign Policy: The Democracy Dimension*, 55–85. Foundation Books, 2009.

²² Bhonsale, Mihir Shekhar, and Dhruv Bansal. *India's Indo-Pacific Strategy: Strengthening Partnerships and Navigating Challenges*. Issue Paper No. 5, October 2024. Jaipur: CUTS International, 2024.

²³ Pushkar Kumar, "Indo-Pacific Geoconstruct – Indian Perspective." *International Journal of Scientific Research and Technology* Vol. 2, (2025), p. 507-518. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15476370>

India and China continue to have a complex relationship. Although trade with China increased, border disputes and security issues persisted. The Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP) was rejected by India in 2019 due to concerns that it would worsen trade deficits and harm Indian businesses. With other accords like the ASEAN-India Free Trade Area, India is still enhancing trade and investment with ASEAN.²⁴ In order to oppose China's BRI and create infrastructure, India also collaborates with nations like Iran, Russia, and Japan. India collaborates with other nations to maintain regional stability and peace.²⁵

VI. India's Approach to the Indo-Pacific

VI.I. India uses several strategies in the region:

1. Act East Policy (2014) to Indo-Pacific: At the ASEAN-India Summit in Myanmar, the Indian government announced India's Act East Policy (AEP). As part of the new realpolitik seen in Indian foreign policy, the AEP was characterised as beckoning 'a strategic shift' in that country's foreign policy and as an effort to establish deeper and closer economic integration with its eastern neighbours. The AEP's main goals were to integrate the economies and security of the region and to fortify ties with East and Southeast Asian nations.²⁶
2. An upgrade from the older 'Look East' policy.: It aims to boost India's economic ties, security partnerships, and cultural links with Southeast Asia (especially ASEAN) and the wider Indo-Pacific. It also strengthens ties with Japan, South Korea, and Australia, promoting a free, open, and inclusive region.
3. SAGAR Vision (2015): Stands for 'Security and Growth for All in the Region.' It focuses on maritime security, working with neighbours,

²⁴ Madhuri Kumari, Ayesha Fatma, and Nalin Bharti, "Why India Forgo RCEP? Analyzing Trade Diversion Effects of Indian FTAs." *Journal of Asia-Pacific Studies*, vol. 6, (2021), p. 301–316

²⁵ Darshana M Baruah, "India's Answer to the Belt and Road: A Road Map for South Asia." *Carnegie India* (August 21, 2018). <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2018/08/indias-answer-to-the-belt-and-road-a-road-map-for-south-asia?lang=en>.

²⁶ Prashanth Parameswaran, "Modi Unveils India's 'Act East Policy' to ASEAN in Myanmar." *The Diplomat*, (November 17, 2014). <https://thediplomat.com/2014/11/modi-unveils-indias-act-east-policy-to-asean-in-myanmar/>.

and sustainable development. Its goals are protecting India's interests, building stronger regional relationships, encouraging peace, and working with other powers.²⁷

4. Indo-Pacific Oceans Initiative (IPOI) (2019): A plan to tackle common challenges in the region, matching ASEAN's vision. It has seven focus areas:

- Maritime Security
- Protecting the Ocean Environment
- Managing Ocean Resources
- Helping Build Skills & Sharing Resources
- Disaster Preparedness & Response
- Science & Technology Cooperation
- Trade, Connectivity & Shipping

India's Indo-Pacific strategy is a carefully planned approach that aims to ensure regional stability and growth. This region, stretching from Africa's eastern shores to the Pacific Ocean, is vital for India's economic interests, sea route security, and geopolitical influence. To secure its interests, India focuses on two key pillars: tackling challenges and deepening partnerships.²⁸

VII. Opportunities in the region

India has to take use of all the economic prospects available in the 'Indo-Pacific Region' (IPR). Enhancing infrastructure, drawing in investments, guaranteeing energy security, fostering the digital economy, and establishing a robust financial system are some ways to do this. High-quality infrastructure is in considerable demand throughout the Indo-Pacific region. Effective and well-designed infrastructure can advance society and the economy. Regional development banks and assistance agencies should contribute sufficient

²⁷ Jivanta Schöttli, "Security and Growth for All in the Indian Ocean – Maritime Governance and India's Foreign Policy." *India Review*, (2019), p. 568-581. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14736489.2019.1703366>.

²⁸ Sayantan Halder, "Time to Reset the Indo-Pacific Oceans Initiative." *Hindustan Times*, (November 19, 2024). <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/time-to-reset-the-indo-pacific-oceans-initiative-10173201277425-amp.html>.

funds to assist nations in achieving sustainable development in order to accomplish this objective.²⁹ However, issues like non-tariff barriers to trade like corruption must be addressed first. Development and commerce may be slowed by these problems. Building capacity, exchanging technical expertise, and promoting collaborations between public and private entities are effective strategies for overcoming difficulties. Strong and long-lasting infrastructure that promotes the region's long-term growth may be built with the aid of these initiatives.

Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs) are another tool that India ought to utilise more effectively. By making it simpler for businesses to operate and invest in the area, these accords can aid in increasing foreign direct investment (FDI). BITs can promote sustainable development, ease constraints, and enhance market access. Regional cooperation and a well-structured investment policy are necessary to draw in additional capital. Lack of collaboration between nations to support cross-border business expansion is one of the Indo-Pacific's weaknesses. An Indo-Pacific Business Forum should be established to promote business collaboration in order to address this. To address the demand for trained people in export industries, programs for skill development must be implemented concurrently. Additionally, these initiatives can boost employee productivity and advance technology.³⁰ By assisting in the establishment of regional organisations like an Indo-Pacific (IP) Regional Investment Framework, IP Business Forum, IP Skill Development Framework, IP Economic Development Fund, and an IP Development Bank, India may play a significant role.³¹ These groups would facilitate coordination, enhance collaboration, and promote equitable and balanced economic growth. Concise and straightforward rules are essential for bettering company circumstances. Starting and

²⁹ Surupa Gupta. "India and the Indo-Pacific Economic Framework." *Asia Pacific Bulletin*, July 21, 2022. <https://scholarspace.manoa.hawaii.edu/items/79b29c54-7407-44d6-a296-a533a12afa20>

³⁰ Christian Wagner, India as a Regional Security Provider in South Asia. *South Asia Scan*, no. 8 (June 2020). German Institute for International and Security Affairs (SWP). <https://www.isas.nus.edu.sg/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/South-Asia-Scan-Vol-8-Full.pdf>

³¹ Ministry of Commerce & Industry, "Indians attended Indo-Pacific Economic Framework for Prosperity (IPEF) Ministerial meeting in Singapore", Press release, 6 Jun 2024. <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleaseIframePage.aspx?PRID=2023211>

operating a company can be made much easier by digitising business registration and guaranteeing sound governance. Additionally, regional establishments should collaborate to advance optimal procedures and raise participation requirements. To facilitate information and technical skill sharing, sub-regions should establish public-private partnerships.³²

VII.I. Tackling Key Challenges

(a). Diversifying Defence Suppliers

Historically reliant on Russian equipment, India is now shifting toward Western arms, including deals involving F-35 jets and naval hardware with U.S. and French partners.³³ This diversification boosts India's ability to respond to regional threats and reduces vulnerability to any one source.

(b). Technological and Cybersecurity Resilience

Rapid developments in cyber-warfare and surveillance highlight the need for Indo-Pacific nations to build robust digital defences. India collaborates with allies to share best practices, improve critical infrastructure security, and reduce risks from cyberattacks.

(c). Non-traditional Threats

Environmental hazards like climate change, maritime piracy, and natural disasters pose significant risks. Through initiatives like SAGAR and the Indo-Pacific Oceans Initiative (IPOI), India supports sustainability, resource management, and maritime rescues—aiming for shared prosperity.³⁴

³² James Nedumpara and Pushkar Reddy, "IPEF's Clean Economy Opportunities." *Gateway House*, (December 5, 2024) <https://www.gatewayhouse.in/ipefs-clean-economy-opportunities/>.

³³ Associated Press, "Guarded Optimism in India as Trump and Modi Outline Plans to Deepen Defense Partnership." *AP News*, February 2025. <https://apnews.com/article/modi-trump-india-us-defense-stealth-aircraft-1aae9a3945a209d910d6169b1f73f5bb>

³⁴ Bhonsale, Mihir Shekhar, and Dhruv Bansal. "India's Indo-Pacific Strategy: Strengthening Partnerships and Navigating Challenges", Issue Paper No. 5, October 2024. Jaipur: CUTS International.

VII. Deepening Strategic Partnerships

(a) India's QUAD vision

India's vision for the Quad, a group including India, the United States, Japan, and Australia, as a 'security community' is based on the idea of a pluralistic security community, as described by Karl Deutsch. This means the countries work together for peace while keeping their independence, rather than uniting into one entity. However, India's approach differs from the other Quad members, affecting how the group functions as a security community.³⁵

The U.S., Japan, and Australia strongly support the Quad as a way to protect a free and open international system based on shared democratic values. However, they have been hesitant to fully include India due to concerns about India's internal politics, which some see as less democratic. India, on the other hand, believes its democracy is rooted in its ancient culture and does not need outside correction.³⁶ Indian leaders also question the idea that a security community must follow the same values as the other Quad members.

India's strategy also differs because it avoids openly opposing China. Unlike the other Quad countries, India does not name China in joint statements with the U.S. or Quad partners. Kenneth Juster, a former U.S. Ambassador to India, noted that India avoids directly challenging China to prevent conflict.³⁷ For example, in his 2018 Shangri-La Dialogue speech, Prime Minister Narendra Modi stressed that India sees the Indo-Pacific as inclusive, not as a limited group aimed at any country, like China.³⁸

³⁵ Kate Sullivan de Estrada, "India and Order Transition in the Indo-Pacific: Resisting the Quad as a 'Security Community.'" *Pacific Review* 36, no. 2, (2023), p. 378-405. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09512748.2022.2160792>

³⁶ *ibid*

³⁷ I. Juster Kenneth, "Farewell Address by Ambassador Kenneth I. Juster: Ambition and Achievement in the U.S.–India Partnership." U.S. Embassy & Consulates in India, (January 5, 2023). <https://in.usembassy.gov/farewell-address-by-ambassador-kenneth-i-juster-ambition-and-achievement-in-the-u-s-india-partnership/>.

³⁸ Narendra Modi, "Keynote Address at the Shangri-La Dialogue". Singapore, Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, (June 1, 2018). <https://www.mea.gov.in/Speeches-Statements.htm>

The other Quad members are more committed to making the Quad a strong security community. When this effort struggles, they turn to other groups like AUKUS (Australia, UK, and U.S.), which share a clearer democratic vision.³⁹ India's reluctance to form traditional alliances and its rejection of external judgments about its democracy shape how the Quad works in the Indo-Pacific. This makes it harder for the Quad to become a tight-knit security community aligned with U.S. ideals. India's membership in the Quad, with the U.S., Japan, and Australia, boosts maritime security through joint exercises, information sharing, and humanitarian missions.⁴⁰

(b). Bilateral Ties with Japan and Singapore

India and Japan enjoy close security cooperation, including naval drills like Malabar, counterterrorism efforts, and nuclear energy collaboration. Likewise, India's defence agreements with Singapore, e.g., SIMBEX and port access arrangements, enhance operational readiness and coordination.⁴¹

(c). Strengthening ASEAN and EU Engagement

India deepens ties with Southeast Asia through ASEAN platforms, maritime projects, and trade deals. Collaboration with the EU includes shared goals like maritime law enforcement, climate action, and technological cooperation.⁴²

<https://www.frstrategie.org/en/publications/notes/india-s-indo-pacific-2018-shangri-dialogue-speech-conceptual-cornerstone-2024>

³⁹ Rajesh Kumar and Aamir Khan, "The Quadrilateral Security Dialogue's Path to Institutionalization: A He and Feng Perspective." *Journal of Indo-Pacific Affairs* 7, no. 3 (May 8, 2024).

<https://www.airuniversity.af.edu/JIPA/Display/Article/3768292/the-quadrilateral-security-dialogues-path-to-institutionalization-a-he-and-feng/>.

⁴⁰ Kersten, Alexander, and Julia Yoon. "Will the 'Strengthening the Quad Act' Work?" *Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS)*, (July 22, 2024).

<https://www.csis.org/analysis/will-strengthening-quad-act-work>

⁴¹ Satoru Nagao and Koh Swee Lean Collin. "A Japan-Singapore-India Maritime Partnership." *The Diplomat*, (February 12, 2016).

<https://thediplomat.com/2016/02/a-japan-singapore-india-maritime-partnership/>.

⁴² Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung (FES). *The Transitioning Security Order in the Indo-Pacific*. (2023). <https://asia.fes.de/news/security-order-indo-pacific.html>

VIII. India's Policy Response to Shifting Indo-Pacific Realities

India's policy response to the changing realities of the Indo-Pacific has evolved steadily over the past few decades. As the Indo-Pacific region becomes more central to global trade, security, and geopolitics, India has adjusted its strategies to reflect these changes. The Indo-Pacific, stretching from the east coast of Africa to the west coast of the Americas, includes many strategic maritime routes, making it important for India's economic and security interests. India sees the Indo-Pacific as a free, open, inclusive, and rules-based region that should not be dominated by any one country. This vision aligns with India's broader goals of promoting regional peace, security, and development.⁴³

India has also built strong relations with regional groupings like the ASEAN and participated actively in platforms such as the East Asia Summit and ASEAN Defence Ministers Meeting Plus (ADMM+). These forums provide India with opportunities to share its concerns, promote dialogue, and work together with other countries to maintain regional security and economic growth.⁴⁴ India has also developed the IPOI, which promotes cooperation in areas like maritime security, disaster response, connectivity, and sustainable development. This initiative reflects India's willingness to contribute to the collective growth and safety of the region.

China's growing military and economic presence in the region, especially in the South China Sea, has also influenced India's policies. India has expressed support for the freedom of navigation and respect for international law, particularly the 'United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea' (UNCLOS). By doing so, India aims to protect its maritime interests and maintain peace in the region without entering into direct confrontation with China.⁴⁵

India's decision to stay out of the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP) in 2019 was also influenced by concerns over

⁴³ Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung (FES). *The Transitioning Security Order in the Indo-Pacific*. (2023). <https://asia.fes.de/news/security-order-indo-pacific.html>

⁴⁴ M. Prayaga, "India-ASEAN Cooperation in the Evolving Regional Mechanisms." *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, Vol. no. 1 (2020), p. 67–81. https://www.ejsss.net.in/print_article.php?did=8088

⁴⁵ Abhijit Singh, "India's Strategic Stakes in the South China Sea." *Asia Policy*, Vol. no. 21 (2016), p. 14–20. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24905084>.

China's economic dominance and the potential negative impact on Indian industries.⁴⁶

In response to these shifting Indo-Pacific realities, India has also increased its partnerships with like-minded countries through strategic frameworks like the Quad, which includes the United States, Japan, and Australia. The QUAD promotes a shared vision of a secure and stable Indo-Pacific. Overall, India's response to the changing dynamics of the Indo-Pacific shows its commitment to playing a responsible and balanced role in ensuring regional cooperation and long-term peace.

IX. Conclusion

This paper has emphasised India's evolving approach toward the Indo-Pacific Region (IPR), focusing on the necessity of fostering multifaceted regional cooperation. India's strategic engagement should not be limited to economic ties but must also incorporate political, cultural, security, and technological dimensions. The Indo-Pacific, characterised by its diversity and shared opportunities as well as challenges, requires collective action to address issues such as maritime insecurity, economic disruptions, and strategic instability. Through strengthened cooperation, the region can achieve a stable and peaceful environment that benefits all stakeholders.

Maritime connectivity still central to this vision. As one of the busiest maritime zones worldwide, the Indo-Pacific depend heavily on safe and efficient sea lanes for trade, investment, and human exchange. Enhancing maritime services, ports, logistics, and shipping, will enhance regional incorporation, cut transport costs, and accelerate shared growth. In this regard, India's SAGAR vision is a praiseworthy initiative aimed at endorsing maritime security, infrastructure development, and cooperative partnerships. It highlights India's commitment to making the Indo-Pacific safer, more stable, and inclusive through collective responsibility.

However, insistent maritime challenges such as border disputes, piracy, terrorism, smuggling, and illegal fishing cannot be undertaken by any single state. Collective efforts in capacity building, technological cooperation, and information sharing are indispensable. By working with partners, particularly the United States, Japan, and Australia, India

⁴⁶ Abraham Wicaksono, "India's Withdrawal from Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP)." *Nation State: Journal of International Studies*, vol. 4 (2021), p. 231–246. <https://doi.org/10.24076/nsjis.v4i2.571>

can strengthen collective responses and underpin the principles of free trade, open markets, and regional connectivity.

Finally, the role of ASEAN is pivotal in shaping this cooperative framework. As an established model of regional diplomacy and integration, ASEAN can act as a vital hub for dialogue, conflict resolution, and infrastructural collaboration across the Indo-Pacific. A deeper India–ASEAN partnership will not only enhance economic interdependence but also serve as the foundation for a peaceful, prosperous, and secure Indo-Pacific order that ensures growth and stability for all.